

INFLUENCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) ON UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN IGNATIUS AJURU UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

The study examines various ways ICT influences the learning activities of students and lecturers in higher institutions. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Two research questions and two research hypotheses were used to guide the study. The population of the study comprised of all students, and lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt, Rivers State. A simple random sampling technique was used to select four hundred and fifty (450) respondents from the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education that is; two hundred and twenty-five (225) undergraduate students and two hundred and twenty-five (225) lecturers. Two research instruments; Students' influence on ICT Questionnaire (SICTQ) and lecturers' influence on ICT Questionnaire (LICTQ) were used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients which were .80 and .81. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to answer hypotheses tested at a 0.05 level of significance. From the results, it was concluded there is no significant influence of information and communication technology of male and female students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education in Port Harcourt. The study also concluded that there is no significant influence of information and communication technology on male and female lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt. Based on the finding, it was recommended that management of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education in Port Harcourt should endeavour to grant access to students to available internet network on campus as it will motivate the students to do their assignment using materials online. It was again, recommended that outdated ICT facilities and equipment should be replaced with modern technology.